

THE DECCAN GEOGRAPHER

Volume 60

Number 3

December 2022

(UGC Care listed: A Peer Review and Refereed Journal)

Chief Editor
Professor B. C. Vaidya

THE DECCAN GEOGRAPHICAL SOCIETY, INDIA
(ESTD : 1962)

CONTENTS

- (1) Applications of RS And GIS for Characterization and Soil Loss Assessment of Tons Watershed in Dehradun District, Garhwal Himalaya 1
– *Dr. P. C. Chanyal*
- (2) Assessment of Groundwater Potential Zones using AHP Technique: A Case Study of Northern Nandurbar District, Maharashtra 16
– *Dr. Mohan. A. Vasave and Mr. Rajesh. B. Valvi*
- (3) Landuse and Population of Begusarai Municipal Corporation in Bihar 30
– *Smriti Divya and Professor R. S. Yadava*
- (4) Assessment of Wetland in Bongaigaon District, Assam 42
– *Anita Shukla, Ashok A. Devikar and Ahidur Rahman*
- (5) Natural Calamities and Migration in India A Stream Wise Analysis 54
– *Dr. Harpreet Singh*
- (6) Climate Change and Food Security in Bundelkhand Region, Madhya Pradesh 63
– *R. P. Mishra*
- (7) Geographical Study of Migration in Tehri Garhwal District, Uttarakhand 76
– *Chet Ram, Devendra Kumar and B. P. Naithani*
- (8) Effect of Industrialisation and Urbanization on Agriculture in India 89
– *Gurpreet Singh Sandhu, Dr. Shital Shukla and Dr. Anil Roy*
- (9) Tourism Assessment of Matheran in Raigad District, Maharashtra State 101
– *Bimla Kumari and Dr. Lokesh Tripathi*
- (10) GIS-Based Geospatial Analysis of Covid-19 in South States in India 112
– *Dr. Ahmad Mujtaba Siddiqui And Zubairul Islam*

Contd...

- (11) Cropping Pattern of Nambiyar Watershed in Tirunelveli District, 124
Tamil Nadu
– *Libina R.S., Jegankumar R., Prakash K., Dhanabalan S.P. and Arya M.A.*
- (12) Assessment of Community Resilience and Natural Hazards in Bhaderwah, 137
Jammu and Kashmir
– *Lucky Sharma, Dr. Chhering Tundup, Anghat Singh and Dr. Narendra Kumar Rana*
-

The Deccan Geographical Society of India
Department of Geography
Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune (Maharashtra)

GIS-BASED GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS OF COVID-19 IN SOUTH STATES IN INDIA

Dr. Ahmad Mujtaba Siddiqui and Zubairul Islam

Abstract

This study analyse the space-time pattern of COVID-19 cases and therefore a space-time cube was created of spatiotemporal COVID-19 data. Statistically significant emerging hotspots were identified using space-time cube as input. The time period of the first wave was determined from 22nd April 2020 to 31st December 2020, and of the second wave from 15th April 2021 to 15th June 2021. The results obtained from the space-time cube show that the overall increasing trend direction was obtained for confirmed cases and deceased cases in both the first and second waves. In the first wave, 19 consecutive and two new hotspots of confirmed cases and 12 consecutive and one new hotspot of death cases were identified. In the second wave, 29 consecutive and three new hotspots of confirmed cases and 12 consecutive and four new hotspots of death cases were found. The study found a strong positive relationship between the variables in confirmed and death cases, as shown by the results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression. The districts having high urban agglomeration in Kerala, Karnataka, and parts of Tamil Nadu got successive high numbers of COVID-19 confirmed cases and deceased cases. Additionally, the spatial pattern of the residuals of confirmed and death cases are statistically significant and highly clustered. The study provides valuable insights into the spatiotemporal trends and patterns of COVID-19 confirmed and death cases during the first and second wave in southern India. The findings can aid policymakers and healthcare professionals in developing effective strategies to manage and control the spread of COVID-19 in these regions.

Introduction

India, with the second-largest population in the world, has been severely affected by COVID-19 disease (Ghosh, Nundy, & Mallick, 2020). As of May 18, 2020, India reported 100,340 confirmed cases and 3155 confirmed deaths due to COVID-19 (Sarkar, Khajanchi, & Nieto, 2020). By June 7, 2021, India's

COVID-19 case tally exceeded 2.89 crore with 1,00,636 new cases reported, while globally, more than 17.40 crore COVID-19 cases have been recorded with 37.44 lakh deaths, with the US accounting for the most (42 percent), followed by India (11 percent) (Moneycontrol, 2021). The causes behind the unprecedented surge in India, including the emergence of particularly infectious variants, unrestricted social interactions, and low vaccine coverage, are being studied by researchers in India (Mallapaty, 2021). Geospatial techniques have been employed by various scholars to study the spatial-temporal pattern of virus spread. Guan et al. (2020) studied the geographical characteristics of those infected by COVID-19. Huang et al. (2020) analyzed the spatiotemporal pattern of COVID-19 and its relationship with epidemiological characteristics, control measures, and their effects. Zhou et al. (2020) used GIS for data mining and confirmed cases reflections. Xiong et al. (2020) used Pearson's correlation methods for spatiotemporal analysis, while Desjardins et al. (2020) employed prospective space-time statistics to identify active and emerging COVID-19 groups at the county level. De Angel Sola et al. (2020) predicted the global spread of COVID-19 based on geographic and climatic data, and Ma et al. (2020) correlated deaths from COVID-19 in Wuhan with climate data and environmental pollution. Hasan and Mahfujul Haque (2020) also studied the correlation between climate and COVID-19 in temperate and tropical countries. The root causes for the spread of COVID-19 pandemic in Uttar Pradesh were mobility of individuals and their physical social networks, as concluded by Tiwari et al. (2020), who proposed a method for visualizing the spatial and chronological aspects of the virus's spread based on geographical information systems (GIS) and Gephi graphs. ArcGIS has several tools for cluster analysis, including Spatially Constrained Multivariate Clustering, Multivariate Clustering, Density-Based Clustering, Image Segmentation, Hot Spot Analysis, Cluster and Outlier Analysis tools, and Space Time Pattern Mining tools (Bennett, 2018). Abad & Orellana (2017) used space-time cubes and spatial statistics to detect and characterize spatiotemporal patterns on volunteered cycling geo-information, which can be used for exploring and analysing cycling mobility patterns in urban areas.

Study Region

The study area for this research is focused on the southern states of India, including Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala. Tamil Nadu is located on the eastern coast of the Indian peninsula and is the seventh-largest state in India by area (Government of Tamil Nadu, 2022). Karnataka is situated in the southwestern

region of India, bordered by the Arabian Sea to the west and the Western Ghats to the east (Government of Karnataka, 2022). Kerala, on the other hand, is a narrow strip of land located along the southwestern coast of India, with the Western Ghats to the east and the Arabian Sea to the west (Government of Kerala, 2022). These states have a combined population of over 200 million people and are known for their diverse culture, geography, and economic activities. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected people worldwide, and India is no exception. As of May 3, 2023, India has recorded over 84 million cases and over 1.1 million deaths due to COVID-19 (World Health Organization, 2022). Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala have been among the most affected states in India, with a total of over 11 million cases and over 160,000 deaths as of May 3, 2023 (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, 2022). The high population density, lack of awareness, and inadequate healthcare facilities in some areas have contributed to the rapid spread of the virus in these states. The purpose of this research is to conduct a geospatial analysis of the spread of COVID-19 in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala. Geospatial analysis is a technique that uses geographic information system (GIS) technology to analyze and visualize spatial data. The research will aim to identify the hotspots and clusters of COVID-19 cases in these states, assess the impact of various control measures implemented by the government, and provide recommendations for future strategies to control the spread of the

Objectives

- (1) To assess the comprehensive study of the spatio-temporal patterns of the pandemic in the study area.
- (2) To study and prepare model the confirmed cases and death cases of the second wave in relation to the first wave.

Database and Methodology

Information on district boundaries was collected from official website of Indian Geo Platform of IISRO, National Remote Sensing Center, Government of India (https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/bhuvan_links.php#) (“ISRO,” 2021). For Covid - 19 Data, the CSV dataset for the duration from March 22nd 2020 to June 15th 2021 was collected from COVID19-India API (<https://api.covid19india.org/>) and the Statistical web portal, Government of India, (<https://www.mygov.in/covid-19>). The data contains everyday number of confirmed, recovered, deceased and tested cases at district level in India (“COVID-19,” 2020). Data management was performed using Excel. The software package used to analyze the data was ArcGIS.

Results and Discussion

Space Time Cube: Confirmed Waves and Death Waves

The results of space time cube are summarised in Table-1. The overall data trend direction is increasing with significant p value.

Table-1: Trend of Confirmed death Cases

	First Wave	Second Wave		First Wave	Second Wave
Confirmed Cases			Death Cases		
Trend direction	Increasing	Increasing	Trend direction	Increasing	Increasing
Trend statistic	4.4572	6.3112	Trend statistic	4.3201	6.2508
Trend p-value	0.0000	0.0000	Trend p-value	0.0000	0.0000

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

Confirmed Cases

Emerging Hot Spot Analysis shows in case of first wave 19 consecutive and 02 new hot spots of confirmed cases and 12 consecutive and 01 new hot spot of deaths cases. Moreover, in case of second wave 29 consecutive and 03 new hot spots were found of confirmed cases and 12 consecutive and 04 new hot spots were found of deaths cases.

Table-2: Emerging Hot Spot

Pattern Types	First Wave		Second Wave	
	Confirmed Cases	Death Cases	Confirmed Cases	Death Cases
New	02	01	03	04
Consecutive	19	12	29	12

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

The districts under consecutive hot spot are Bengaluru Rural, Mandya, Ramanagara, Kodagu, Chikkaballapura, Tumakuru and Kolar from Karnataka; Palakkad, Kozhikode, Thrissur, Ernakulam, Alappuzha, Kannur, Kottayam, Kollam, Wayanad and Malappuram from Kerala; Krishnagiri from Tamil Nadu. The districts under New Hot Spot are Mysuru from Karnataka and Idukki from Kerala.

The districts under consecutive hot spot are Chikkaballapura, Dakshina Kannada, Kodagu, Kolar, Mandya, Ramanagara, Chamarajanagara, Mysuru, Tumakuru, Bengaluru Rural from Karnataka; Alappuzha, Ernakulam, Idukki, Kannur, Kollam, Kottayam, Malappuram, Palakkad, Pathanamthitta, Thiruvananthapuram, Thrissur, Wayanad from Kerala; Coimbatore, Erode, Krishnagiri, Perambalur, Tiruchirappalli, Tiruppur and Kanyakumari from Tamil Nadu. The districts under New Hot Spot are Mysuru from Karnataka and Idukki from Kerala. Dakshina Kannada and Hassan from Karnataka; Kasaragod from Kerala; Tirunelveli from Tamil Nadu.

Death Cases

The districts under consecutive hot spot category in case of death cases during first wave are Bengaluru Urban, Bengaluru Rural, Mandya, Ramanagara, Kodagu, Chikkaballapura, Krishnagiri, Hassan, Tumakuru, Kolar, Dakshina Kannada from Karnataka; Kannur from Kerala. Only one district Mysuru from Karnataka was found under New Hot Spot category during the first wave. The districts under consecutive hot spot category in case of deceased cases during second wave are Chikkaballapura, Kolar, Mandya, Ramanagara, Bengaluru Urban, Tumakuru and Bengaluru Rural in Karnataka; Palakkad, Thiruvananthapuram and Thrissur in Kerala; Krishnagiri and Tiruchirappalli in Tamil Nadu. Four districts were found under New Hot Spot category two from Kerala as Ernakulam and Kannur and while two from Karnataka as Kodagu and Mysuru.

Modelling and Spatial Relationship

Confirmed Cases: Relation with first wave

The results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression show the positive and strong relationship in between both the variables. The Coefficient of dependent (intercept) variable as 5902.32 and Coefficient of independent variable as 0.0000 represents the positive and strong relationship between explanatory variable and the dependent variable. The results of Probability ($p < 0.0000$) and Robust Probability ($p < 0.000000$) indicate coefficient is statistically significant. The Koenker (BP) Statistic test is not statistically significant ($p = 20.58$), so the relationships modelled is consistent. Jarque-Bera Statistic test is also not statistically significant ($p = 619.73$) so model predictions are not biased (the residuals are closed to normally distributed). As per the spatial relationship OLS model report abnormally high confirmed cases were found the Ernakulam district of Kerala. Here total numbers of confirmed cases were found as 334871 during

second wave till 15th June 2021, whereas as per the model only 254514 were predicted. So, it got the highest number of residuals 80357. The other towns in between 1.6 standard residuals to 01 standard residuals are Coimbatore, Erode, Tiruppur and Tiruchirappalli from Tamil Nadu; Palakkad, Malappuram, Kozhikode, Kottayam, Kollam, Thiruvananthapuram, Thrissur, Kannur, Idukki, Pathanamthitta from Kerala; Bengaluru Urban, Tumakuru, Chikkaballapura, Kolar, Mandya and Mysuru from Karnataka. On the other side spatial relationship OLS model reported very less confirmed cases were there in the Chennai district of Tamil Nadu. Here total numbers of confirmed cases were found as 525826 till 15th June 2021, whereas as per the model only 677258 were predicted. So, it got the less number of residuals - 151432. The other towns in between -1 standard residuals to -0.5 standard residuals are Thiruvallur, Cuddalore, Kancheepuram, Vellore, Salem and Pudukkottai from Tamil Nadu; Ballari, Dakshina Kannada, Davanagere, Haveri, Tiruvannamalai, Theni, Chitradurga from Karnataka.

Death Cases: Relation with Second Wave

The results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression show the positive and strong relationship in between both the variables. The Coefficient of dependent (intercept) variable as -21.73 and Coefficient of independent variable as 0.0000 represents the positive and strong relationship between explanatory variable and the dependent variable. The results of Probability ($p < 0.0000$) and Robust Probability ($p < 0.000000$) indicate coefficient is statistically significant. The Koenker (BP) Statistic test is not statistically significant ($p = 71.71$), so the relationships modelled is consistent. Jarque-Bera Statistic test is also not statistically significant ($p = 1750.57$) so model predictions are not biased (the residuals are closed to normally distributed). As per the spatial relationship OLS model report abnormally high death cases were found in the Bengaluru Urban district of Karnataka with 5.6 of standard residuals. Here total numbers of death cases were found as 15319 during second wave till 15th June 2021, whereas as per the model only 11929 were predicted. So, it got the highest number of residuals 3389. The other towns in between 1 standard residuals to 0.5 standard residuals are Thiruvananthapuram, Palakkad, Kozhikode, Thrissur and Ernakulam from Kerala; Tiruchirappalli from Tamil Nadu. On the other side spatial relationship OLS model reported very less death cases were there in the Chennai district of Tamil Nadu with -5.3 of the standard residuals. Here total numbers of death cases were found as 7854 till 15th June 2021, whereas as per the model only 11066 were predicted. So, it got the less number of residuals - 3212. The other towns in between -1.7

Fig. 1

standard residuals to -0.5 standard residuals are Dakshina Kannada, Mysuru, Dharwad, Davanagere, Koppal from Karnataka. Interestingly, there is no district in Kerala under this category. The above Histogram (Fig. 7) shows the residuals how each variable is distributed. Ideally the histogram of residuals would match the normal curve, indicated above (Fig. 7) in blue. Since Jarque-Bera Statistic tests are not statistically significant (Confirmed cases $p = 619.73$, Death cases $p = 1750.57$), so models' predictions are not biased. In case of confirmed cases the outlier towards negative side represents Chennai in Tamil Nadu while the outlier bar towards positive side represents the Ernakulam district from Kerala. In case of death cases the outlier towards negative side represents Chennai in Tamil Nadu while the outlier bar towards positive side represents the Bengaluru urban district from Karnataka.

Spatial Pattern of Residuals

Confirmed Cases and Death Cases

Spatial Pattern of the residuals of confirmed cases is highly clustered (Figure 8). The obtained z-score of 5.78, confirm that there is less than 1% likelihood that this clustered pattern could be the result of random chance. So we can reject the null hypothesis for the Global Moran's I statistic, that the residuals being analysed is not randomly distributed among the features in the study area. Global Moran's Index was found as 0.44, Expected Index - 0.013, Variance 0.006115, z-score 5.77 and p-value 0.000000. Spatial Pattern of the residuals of death cases is also very clustered. The obtained z-score of 1.86, confirm that there is less than 1% likelihood that this clustered pattern could be the result of random chance. So, in this case also we can reject the null hypothesis for the Global Moran's I statistic, that the residuals being analysed is not randomly distributed among the features in the study area. Global Moran's Index was found as 0.118, Expected Index -0.013, Variance 0.0049, z-score 1.86 and p-value 0.062.

Conclusion

The major research question answered in the present work was to find the spatial and temporal variability in term of corona conformed cases and deceased cases at district level. The research explored the potential use of space time pattern mining tool provided by ArcGIS platform for geospatial analysis. The results indicate Kerala was the hardest hit during the second wave of corona compare to Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. The findings will be helpful for all stockholders working to minimise the Corona problem.

Fig. 2

References

- Abad, L., & Orellana, D. (2017, December). Exploring space-time patterns of volunteered cycling data in an intermediate city. In V CONGRESO REDU (p. 421).
- ArcGIS. (2021). An overview of the Space Time Pattern Mining toolbox—ArcGIS Pro Documentation. Retrieved June 12, 2021, from Arcgis.com website: <https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/2.7/tool-reference/space-time-pattern-mining/an-overview-of-the-space-time-pattern-mining-toolbox.htm>
- Census of India (2021). Retrieved June 13, 2021, from Censusindia.gov.in website: https://censusindia.gov.in/Census_And_You/area_and_population.aspx
- COVID-19. (2020, March 16). Retrieved June 9, 2021, from MyGov.in website: <https://www.mygov.in/covid-19>
- ESRI. (2021). Create Space Time Cube by Aggregating Points (Space Time Pattern Mining)—ArcGIS Pro | Documentation. Retrieved August 24, 2021, from Arcgis.com website: <https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/space-time-pattern-mining/create-space-time-cube.htm>
- Express News Service. (2021, June 12). UP: Active cases drop below 10,000 as aggressive jab strategy continues to slow Covid spread. Retrieved June 13, 2021, from The Indian Express website: <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/lucknow/up-active-cases-drop-below-10000-as-aggressive-jab-strategy-continues-to-slow-covid-spread-7356477/>
- Ghosh, A., Nundy, S., & Mallick, T. K. (2020). How India is dealing with COVID-19 pandemic. *Sensors International*, 1, 100021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sintl.2020.100021>
- Government of Tamil Nadu. (2022). About Tamil Nadu. Retrieved from <https://www.tn.gov.in/about-tamil-nadu.html>
- Government of Karnataka. (2022). About Karnataka. Retrieved from <https://karnataka.gov.in/page/About+Karnataka/en>
- Government of Kerala. (2022). About Kerala. Retrieved from <https://kerala.gov.in/about-kerala>
- Guan, W. J., Ni, Z. Y., Hu, Y., Liang, W. H., Ou, C. Q., He, J. X., ... & Zhong, N. S. (2020). Clinical characteristics of coronavirus disease 2019 in China. *New England journal of medicine*, 382(18), 1708-1720.
- Hasan, N. A., & Haque, M. M. (2020). Predict the next moves of COVID-19: reveal the temperate and tropical countries scenario. medRxiv.
- ISRO. (2021). Retrieved June 9, 2021, from Nrsc.gov.in website: https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/bhuvan_links.php#
- Moneycontrol. (2021). CORONAVIRUS. Retrieved June 13, 2021, from Moneycontrol website: <https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/coronavirus/in-charts-indias-covid-19-case-count-state-wise-trends-vaccination-data-and-other-key-details-5-6996121.html>
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (2022). COVID-19 Dashboard. Retrieved from <https://www.mygov.in/covid-19>
- Sarkar, K., Khajanchi, S., & Nieto, J. J. (2020). Modeling and forecasting the COVID-19 pandemic in India. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 139, 110049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110049>
- Tiwari, A., & Aljoufie, M. (2021). A qualitative geographical information system interpretation of mobility and COVID-19 pandemic intersection in Uttar Pradesh, India. *Geospatial Health*, 16(1).
- Worldometers. (2021). India COVID. Retrieved June 12, 2021, from Worldometers.info website: <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/country/india/>

World Health Organization. (2022). COVID-19 Situation Dashboard. Retrieved from <https://covid19.who.int/>

Xiong, Y., Wang, Y., Chen, F., & Zhu, M. (2020). Spatial statistics and influencing factors of the novel coronavirus pneumonia 2019 epidemic in Hubei Province, China.

Zhou, C., Su, F., Pei, T., Zhang, A., Du, Y., Luo, B., ... & Xiao, H. (2020). COVID-19: challenges to GIS with big data. *Geography and sustainability*, 1(1), 77-87.

--Dr. Ahmad Mujtaba Siddiqui,
Assistant Professor,
Department of Geography,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh
(Uttar Pradesh)

--Zubairul Islam,
Associate Professor,
Department of Geography and Environmental
Studies,
CSSH, Adigrat University,
(Ethiopia)